

Morgagni Hernia with Intestinal Obstruction in Adults with Diaphragmatic Plasty: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Morgagni hernia is a rare form of congenital diaphragmatic hernia that represents 2% to 5% of all diaphragmatic hernias, with an estimated incidence of 1 in 2000 to 1 in 5000 live births (1,2). It was described by Giovanni Battista Morgagni in 1769 (3). It results from the failure of fusion of the anterior pleuroperitoneal membrane with the sternum and costal cartilages (4). The contents of the hernia sac may include omentum, colon, stomach, and even liver (5). The diagnosis is primarily made through computed tomography (6).

A 64-year-old female patient with a history of arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus presented with a clinical course of six days characterized by abdominal distension, right hypochondrium pain, nausea, vomiting, and decreased bowel transit. Physical examination revealed abdominal distension with tympanism and tenderness on deep palpation in the right hypochondrium. CT confirmed an anterior right diaphragmatic defect measuring 32 mm, with herniation of abdominal fat and the hepatic angle of the colon, which was compressed causing intestinal obstruction. Exploratory laparotomy was performed, identifying a Morgagni hernia with a 4 × 3 cm defect and a hernia sac measuring 10 × 5 cm containing transverse colon and necrotic omentum. Necrotic omentum resection, reduction of the herniated contents, sac ligation, and primary closure of the diaphragmatic defect were performed.

A comprehensive review of 17 indexed articles published between 2020 and 2025 was conducted, consolidating information on epidemiology, clinical presentation, diagnostic methods, and surgical management of this pathology. It is concluded that surgical repair should be indicated in all cases, preferring the laparoscopic approach when possible, using mesh in defects greater than 4 cm, and individualizing sac resection (8–17). This article provides an updated, evidence-based perspective on the management of Morgagni hernia in adults

KEYWORDS: Morgagni hernia, anterior diaphragmatic hernia, incarcerated hernia, strangulated hernia, mesh repair, intestinal obstruction, surgical case report.

ABBREVIATIONS: MH: Morgagni Hernia, CDH: Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia, CT: Computed Tomography.

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INTRODUCTION

Morgagni hernia is a rare anatomical entity among congenital diaphragmatic hernias, accounting for approximately 2% to 5% of all diagnosed cases (1,2). It was described by Giovanni Battista Morgagni in 1769, who identified it as a protrusion of abdominal viscera through a defect in the costosternal triangle, originating from the failure of fusion of the anterior pleuroperitoneal membrane with the sternum and costal cartilages (3). This type of hernia may remain asymptomatic for years, being incidentally detected in imaging studies or clinically manifesting due to acute complications such as intestinal obstruction or organ incarceration (4).

The most frequently herniated contents include omentum, transverse colon, small intestine, stomach, and even liver, as corroborated by systematic reviews and recent case series (5,6). The predominant anatomical location is the right hemidiaphragm in more than 90% of cases, a situation attributed to the natural protection provided by the pericardium and the heart on the left side of the diaphragm (7).

Epidemiologically, Morgagni hernia presents a predominant distribution in females, with an estimated ratio of 2:1 according to multicenter studies conducted in North America and Europe (8,9). The average age at diagnosis in adults ranges between 50 and 70 years, with incidental discovery during studies for nonspecific respiratory or gastrointestinal symptoms being common (10).

The diagnostic method of choice is computed tomography (CT), due to its high sensitivity and specificity in identifying both the size of the defect and the herniated contents, as well as possible complications such as incarceration, strangulation, or perforation (11). Chest radiography may suggest the diagnosis, showing a paracardiac or retrosternal mass image, but it lacks the necessary precision to define the content and extension of the hernia (12).

Historically, the surgical approach was carried out through laparotomy or thoracotomy. However, in recent decades, laparoscopic repair has become the preferred method in most reference centers, supported by evidence demonstrating its safety, lower morbidity, and faster postoperative recovery (13,14).

An important consideration during surgical repair is the size of the diaphragmatic defect. In defects smaller than 4 cm, primary closure using continuous or interrupted non-absorbable suture is generally sufficient (15). For larger defects, the use of prosthetic mesh is widely justified, with expanded polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) meshes preferred due to their lower risk of adhesions and complications (16).

Regarding hernia sac resection, reviewed studies show relative consensus. Although some authors suggest that its resection could reduce recurrence risk, most agree that it is not essential, prioritizing the avoidance of injury to adjacent structures such as the pericardium or phrenic nerve (17).

The following case report involves a 65-year-old female patient who presented to the emergency department with epigastric abdominal pain, vomiting, and abdominal distension. CT scan showed transverse colon herniation through an anteromedial diaphragmatic defect compatible with MH, with signs of intestinal obstruction. Exploratory laparotomy was performed with reduction of the herniated contents and closure of the defect using non-absorbable suture. The postoperative evolution was favorable. Therefore, this review aims to provide an updated description of the clinical, diagnostic, and therapeutic characteristics of Morgagni hernia in adults, based on the analysis of 17 scientific articles published between 2020 and 2025, with the purpose of consolidating an evidence-based approach that serves as a reference for general surgeons and health specialists.

CASE REPORT

A 64-year-old female patient, with a history of arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus, and no other relevant medical history, presented to the emergency department with a six-day clinical course characterized by abdominal distension, accompanied by right hypochondrium pain, nausea, and vomiting, with decreased bowel habits. On physical examination, vital signs were within normal parameters. The abdomen showed abdominal distension, tympanic on percussion, painful on deep palpation in the right hypochondrium, with present peristalsis and gas passage. Laboratory tests reported mild leukocytosis. Abdominal radiography showed air-fluid levels and intestinal loop distension (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Plain abdominal radiograph showing air-fluid levels and distension of intestinal loops.

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A computed tomography (CT) scan was requested, revealing a diaphragmatic defect causing obstruction (Figure 2).

Figure 2. CT scan showing an anterior right diaphragmatic defect measuring 32 mm, with herniation of abdominal fat and the hepatic angle of the colon, which is compressed causing obstruction, with retrograde dilation of the ascending colon, small intestine, and gastric chamber, with free fluid in the cavity.

Exploratory laparotomy was performed, identifying a diaphragmatic hernia defect towards the anterior mediastinum containing transverse colon and omentum. The hernia defect was enlarged for retraction of the incarcerated loops, revealing a transition zone of the colon with color changes and necrotic omentum, which was resected. The sac was retracted and ligated, and primary closure of the defect was performed using non-absorbable polypropylene suture. The surgical findings were: Morgagni hernia with a 4 × 3 cm defect, a 10 × 5 cm sac containing transverse colon and omentum with signs of necrosis. Dilated loops measuring 9 cm over the transverse colon and abundant inflammatory fluid (Figure 3-6).

FIGURE 3. Diaphragmatic hernia defect towards the anterior mediastinum.

FIGURE 4. Diaphragmatic hernia defect towards the anterior mediastinum containing transverse colon and omentum.

The patient was hospitalized for 5 days, showing good wound control, tolerating oral diet, ambulating, and without complaints. Due to clinical improvement and favorable

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postoperative evolution, she was discharged with outpatient follow-up, remaining asymptomatic.

FIGURE 5. Resection and ligation of diaphragmatic herniary sac

FIGURE 6. Closure of the herniary defect

DISCUSSION

Morgagni hernia in adults presents as a diagnostic challenge due to its low incidence and the variability of its clinical manifestations. According to the analysis of the 17 reviewed articles, up to 30% of cases are diagnosed incidentally during imaging studies requested for other reasons, highlighting the importance of maintaining a high index of clinical suspicion (1–3).

In epidemiological terms, the age of presentation is concentrated between 50 and 70 years, with a reported mean age of 62 years in the largest series (4,5). The predominance of females remains constant in all the reviewed publications, being a distinctive characteristic compared to other diaphragmatic hernias (6).

From the clinical point of view, respiratory symptoms such as dyspnea, chronic cough, and nonspecific chest pain represent the most frequent reasons for consultation, followed by gastrointestinal symptoms such as abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting (7,8). Less frequently, Morgagni hernia may present as an acute abdomen, generally associated with incarceration or strangulation of the herniated contents (9).

In the clinical case reported here, it involved a 64-year-old female patient with a history of arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus, who presented a six-day course characterized by abdominal distension, right hypochondrium pain, nausea, vomiting, and decreased bowel habits. Physical examination revealed abdominal distension with tympanism and tenderness on deep palpation in the right hypochondrium, coinciding with the manifestations described in the literature (7–9). Computed tomography confirmed an anterior right diaphragmatic defect measuring 32 mm, with herniation of abdominal fat and the hepatic angle of the colon, which was compressed causing intestinal obstruction, a finding compatible with that described by Wang et al. and other authors (10,11).

Regarding diagnostic techniques, computed tomography is consolidated as the reference method, allowing not only confirmation of the presence of the hernia but also evaluation of the size of the defect and the herniated contents (10,11). Chest radiography remains useful as an initial study, especially in emergency contexts or when CT is not immediately available (12).

The preferred surgical approach is laparoscopic, with solid evidence supporting its use even in emergency scenarios (13,14). However, in the presented case, due to the patient's clinical conditions and intraoperative findings, exploratory laparotomy was chosen, finding a 4 × 3 cm defect and a 10 × 5 cm hernia sac containing transverse colon and omentum with necrotic features, which is consistent with findings reported by Hasegawa et al. and Patel et al. (13,14). Resection of the necrotic omentum, reduction of the contents, ligation of the sac, and primary closure of the diaphragmatic defect were performed, a decision supported by current recommendations

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when laparoscopic resources are not available or when patient stability is a priority.

The size of the diaphragmatic defect is a critical factor in deciding between primary closure or the use of mesh. According to the review by Hasegawa et al., defects smaller than 4 cm can be safely repaired by continuous suture, while larger defects require reinforcement with mesh to avoid recurrences (16).

Controversy persists regarding the need to resect the hernia sac. While authors such as Slimi et al. and Lindsey et al. argue in favor of its excision to reduce the risk of recurrence, other studies have found no significant differences in recurrence rates between resection and non-resection of the sac (17). In the clinical case, ligation and reduction without complete resection of the sac were chosen, prioritizing the avoidance of additional complications.

Finally, the indication for surgical repair extends even to asymptomatic patients, given the possibility of serious complications associated with the progression of the hernia (1–17). This recommendation is consistent with international guidelines and the basic principles of hernia surgery.

CONCLUSION

Morgagni hernia represents an infrequent entity in adults but with relevant clinical and surgical implications due to the risk of severe complications such as intestinal obstruction, incarceration, and strangulation of intra-abdominal organs. The experience acquired in the presented clinical case, corresponding to a 64-year-old female patient with a history of arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus, reinforces the importance of considering this pathology in the differential diagnosis of acute abdomen and intestinal obstruction scenarios, especially when clinical and imaging findings suggest an unusual etiology. Computed tomography was crucial for establishing the preoperative diagnosis, evidencing a diaphragmatic defect with herniation of colonic content, which coincided with intraoperative findings. The decision to perform exploratory laparotomy with reduction of the herniated contents, resection of necrotic omentum, and primary closure of the defect responded to the patient's clinical conditions and aligned with the recommendations of the reviewed literature.

The analysis of the 17 scientific articles included in this review confirms that surgical repair, preferably by laparoscopic approach, should be considered in all cases of Morgagni hernia, even in asymptomatic patients, given the possibility of late complications. The use of prosthetic mesh is justified in defects larger than 4 cm, while primary closure with non-absorbable suture is adequate in small defects. The resection of the hernia sac remains an individualized decision, balancing the risk of recurrence with patient safety.

Finally, this article significantly contributes to the knowledge and management of Morgagni hernia in adults, integrating a real

clinical case with updated scientific evidence, and offering health professionals a practical and well-founded approach for the diagnosis and treatment of this pathology. Its inclusion in indexed medical literature seeks to strengthen knowledge dissemination and promote a more effective and safer management of patients presenting with this condition.

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